

Appendix

Figure A1: MEDIA's application landscape over time

Figure A2: MANUFACTURING's application landscape over time

Table A1: Comparison of Linear, Quadratic, Cubic Panel Regression Models
Dependent variable: Growth in degree

	Linear Model (1)	Growth Quadratic Model (2)	Cubic Model (3)
Degree	0.42*** (0.04)	0.53*** (0.05)	1.00*** (0.08)
Degree ²		-0.003*** (0.001)	-0.04*** (0.005)
Degree ³			0.0004*** (0.0001)
Age(days)	-0.0002*** (0.0001)	-0.0002*** (0.0001)	-0.0001*** (0.0001)
AIC	2608.03	2599.2	2527.17
BIC	3612.1	3607.86	3540.41
Observations	724	724	724
R ²	0.21	0.22	0.30
F Statistic	67.10*** (df = 2; 505)	47.85*** (df = 3; 504)	53.21*** (df = 4; 503)

Note:

* ** p*** p<0.01

Table A2: Decommissioning Model (Study 1)

	<i>Dependent variable: Decommissioning</i>
Heavy system	-2.393** (1.041)
Growth pattern: Stable	-0.950** (0.394)
Growth pattern: Growing	-1.154** (0.554)
Period: 2016-2018	0.737* (0.425)
Period: 2018-2020	1.263*** (0.401)
Period: 2020-2024	-16.507 (758.037)
Constant	-2.052*** (0.488)
Observations	724
Log Likelihood	-171.809
Akaike Inf. Crit.	357.617
<i>Note:</i>	* p < 0.05 ** p < 0.01 *** p < 0.001